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THE WAYS TO MAKE LEARNING ENGLISH MORE INTERESTING

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Abstract. The article reveals the issue of effective teaching English that concerns the majority of scholar of the field. Due to the rapid development of technologies and their application to the process it is going to make teaching-learning English be more interesting and productive.

Keywords: *enthusiasm, productive skills, communicative competence, meaningful conversations, numerous strategies, diverse technological options.*

In recent times, there has been a noticeable rise in students' enthusiasm for foreign languages. Over the last two decades, educators have increasingly emphasized the development of spoken language skills. Foreign language curricula now prioritize productive skills, particularly emphasizing communicative competence. The ability of students to participate in meaningful conversations in the target language is now recognized as a crucial, if not the most significant, objective of language education. This change in focus has led to a heightened demand for instructional materials that facilitate controlled interactive speaking practice beyond the traditional classroom setting [2].

Enhancing the appeal of English instruction is crucial, focusing on discovering methods to render the subject more captivating for learners. In the absence of active involvement, the likelihood of significant learning diminishes. Numerous strategies exist to augment the subject's interest, emphasizing the importance of identifying approaches that suit both the educator and students. Initiating this process, consider the following suggestions:

1. Integrate real-life instances: Facilitating comprehension is easier when students can relate the material to their own experiences. Incorporating real-life examples into lessons can substantially enhance engagement.

2. Foster interactivity: Sustaining student interest involves creating interactive lessons, spanning from group collaborations to participation in various activities.

3. Utilize technology: Leveraging technology proves effective in captivating students and injecting an element of enjoyment into the learning process. Explore the diverse technological options available for classroom integration.

4. Embrace creativity: Encourage inventive teaching approaches without hesitation. A creative approach to presenting material significantly increases the likelihood of student engagement.

These are just a few ideas to get you started. If you can find ways to make English more interesting for your students, you'll be well on your way to teaching it effectively. If you want to share your language and culture with students who are eager and enthusiastic about learning, you should consider becoming an ESL teacher. True, it isn't as simple as it appears, but you can become an ESL teacher with a little practice and some time. Making your [ESL lessons](#) relevant to your students is one of the most important aspects of the ESL curriculum. Preparing material for each level of ESL is critical to ensuring that you meet the needs of the learners. Reading, discussion, writing, and pronunciation are some of the most important skills to learn in English as a Second Language. It is just as important to plan a lesson as it is to teach it. When selecting material for your lesson, you must consider how your students are learning to become better at English. You can teach students how to develop sounds in their speech so that when speaking in English abroad or in a business presentation, they understand them. You can begin planning for a successful PPP project by developing a clear strategy. Your students will have a greater say in how you plan to spend their time. So, as you can see, your students gradually begin to leave the nest. Reading lessons should not test students in any way. It is beneficial for students to participate in activities related to reading. It is possible to develop a few [ESL skills](#) as you progress. There are numerous excellent ESL lesson plans available for ESL teachers to use. Students in the [ESL program](#) want to develop the skills necessary to communicate effectively in English. Students will be given the opportunity to express their opinion on the topic of celebrity in this discussion lesson. This fun activity encourages students to develop their English vocabulary while also improving their English expression. It is common for English learners' writing skills to fall through the cracks in ESL classes. Allowing your students to hone their writing skills will help them improve their communication skills. In addition to asking questions, they can comment on online discussions. They can Tweet and update Facebook statuses using it. During language classes, students must demonstrate their ability to speak a foreign language. Although some [ESL students](#) may find it difficult to pronounce words, you should

continue to work with them to ensure they understand what they are saying. This resource can be used to create your own pronunciation lessons, depending on your individual requirements. Turn to page 17 of the pronunciation resource to learn the words R and L and use these examples in your presentation. Students should come up with their own English tongue twisters for the stage. It is even possible to divide the class into two groups and have them compete using team-based points to correctly sound off each tongue twister [3].

CLT, or **Collaborative Language Teaching**, is an emerging method of language teaching. This type of teaching method is the most popular in the world for English language teaching. The course is primarily designed to help students hone their language skills in the real world by putting them in situations that will help them use them. It is critical to prepare any language for its success. In order to succeed in learning a language, such as English, you must be familiar with grammar, sentence structure, and proper word pronunciation. There are numerous ways to teach English to a child that will provide a solid foundation for learning the language. The following are ten different ways to teach English. One of the most popular methods of English instruction is the **communicative language teaching** (CLT). Students are able to communicate effectively in the real world by utilizing real-time scenarios. The silent method of English teaching focuses on the student's learning over the teacher's. A strong emphasis is placed on listening and speaking abilities in this method. The total physical response (TPR) concept entails using language objects as instructions. Suggestopedia is a method of learning English that incorporates art and music. The Cooperative Language Learning (CLL) program aims to make it easy for shy and timid learners to feel at ease when learning English. The CLL program focuses on students as a whole in order to provide an **English education**. A cooperative learning environment is fostered in the classroom by small groups of students collaborating. The structural method employs traditional methods such as direct methods and grammar translations to effectively teach English. When teaching a new language, words and phrases must be drilled and repeated. In the classroom, it is critical to discover new resources that will aid in the stimulation of original ideas. It is important to engage students in learning a new language; here are some of the top language teaching books that will provide you with new ideas and allow you to learn a new language in a whole new way. Students who are proficient in pronunciation are better able to communicate clearly and confidently in the target language. It is critical to develop a soundproof listening skill in order to understand and speak properly. When you introduce the sounds of an alphabet to a

student, he or she will benefit from the content of the following **English lessons**. Students can understand the sound system of a target language thanks to phonics being included in the curriculum. The program not only improves key language skills like reading, listening, and speaking, but it also helps with other **fundamental language skills**. Successful teaching requires patience and perseverance. When you teach English, you can't help but feel extremely fortunate.

There are many things that need to be covered when teaching English as a second language. The basics include grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure. However, there are also other important aspects of the language such as culture and idioms. It is important to tailor the lessons to the needs of the students.

Teaching English to a beginner can frighten new TEFL teachers. Students who are relatively new to English are referred to as beginners. Family names, household objects, and basic adjectives are some of the most important vocabulary words that a beginner should learn. It is possible for Advanced Advanced English students to communicate and fine tune their language skills in a simple manner. Students all over the world come to study with this group of students [3]. The use of props will benefit beginners in every way. Props and realia (real-life objects) can be used to teach vocabulary, serve as the foundation for an activity or game, or serve as a test. A role-playing game is one of the best ways for adult beginners to learn about real-world situations. The new Micro-credential course in Games and Activities for the Online Classroom (Young Learners) from Bridge offers many useful ideas for teaching English to children using technology. It's not uncommon for children to find anything funny and silly to play with, such as action words, animals, and even silly objects. You can use these ESL songs and activities to motivate your students.

Experienced language teachers know that individual learners have distinct sets of personality characteristics which determine their talents, abilities, and preferences in language learning: some learners are «quick», some are thoughtful, some love to work independently, others requires explanations, guidance, and constant attention from the teacher. That's why we must use the most effective teaching methods and aids at our disposal. Role-plays, language skills, projects, video situations, games, activities can greatly widen our horizons of creativity within the suggested methods. Nowadays the whole English Language Teaching community is entering a new stage of interactive learning by means of new technologies.

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